

Quantum Free Particle Energy and Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and SPN, Messina Dec. 2, 2023

The quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is formally the eigenfunction of the operator $-i\hbar d/dx$, which is linked to the translation operator d/dx , and is complex, indicating motion in one direction. For a bound state, however, one takes a linear superposition; $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ with p and $-p$ included, with a fixed parity so $a(p) = a(-p)$ or $a(p) = -a(-p)$, leading to a real wavefunction $W(x)$. This begs the question: What does a real wavefunction imply? Classically, the particle moves to the right for an interval of time and then to the left etc. This suggests two complex wavefunctions indicating different directions at different times, but if one does not follow the particle in time and averages the two motions, then on average there is no motion to the left or right, hence the real wavefunction. This approach involves energy considerations and ignores directional motion which has the same energy, i.e. p and $-p$ have the same kinetic energy.

In this note, we wish to examine this situation in more detail. In (1), we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic probability in that it describes motion in one direction as being dependent on p and x . Here we argue that in terms of energy, all information is contained in either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, one does not need the complex dynamic feature. This does not mean, as we argued in previous notes, that there is no motion in one direction or another, especially at high energy levels. A quantum particle should be consistent with a classical one in the large energy level limit according to the correspondence principle. As a result, we argue that even though formally $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2\cos(px)$, one may directly use $\cos(px)$ (or $\sin(px)$ depending on parity) to create an average kinetic energy in a conservation of energy equation $Ke_{ave} + V(x) = E$. Energy conservation is not concerned with direction of motion. Given that one takes an average, this is a statistical situation and one may consider an entropy linked to energy. If $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, by itself is sufficient to describe average energy, then we argue that this same probability may be used to calculate a free particle entropy over half a cycle in which $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ is strictly positive. We have suggested this recipe for a free particle entropy before (2), but gave no reason for only using part of $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ has a modulus of 1. As a result, it seems that there are two different entropies, one linked with spatial position and another with energy, even for a free particle, but also for a bound one.

Quantum Free Particle Motion

Classically, a particle moves in one direction and changes may occur in tiny dx regions. Newton's second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}$, suggests that it is momentum which responds to force, even though velocity changes too. As a result, we suggest that a free particle should be characterized by p because one does not know at what point a force might appear. Furthermore, a free particle represents steady state motion in time and space.

Quantum mechanics seems to take the view that a free particle represents steady state motion in time, but separates the spatial and temporal steady state motions. It associates motion in space with the translation operator d/dx partial and in time, with d/dt partial. This implies the existence of a function of x which is periodic, with spatial periods (wavelengths) not necessarily fitting in Newton's tiny dx regions. This periodicity, associated with a given p , may be described in two dimensions by a constant radius, representing the fact that all x points carry the same weight spatially, but with components $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. Thus, a quantum free particle is described by:

$$\cos(px) + i \sin(px) \quad ((1))$$

((1)) implies two types of probabilities. By itself, ((1)) is a function of x and depends on a constant p . This description is linked to momentum, energy and interactions as p was included because of interactions in the first place. If one is only interested in motion in space, then this is the usual classical steady state motion which does not depend on x , so the modulus of ((1)) is 1. As a result,

there is a dichotomy which is not present in classical mechanics. Furthermore, the two dimensional form of ((1)) allows one to have p and $-p$ represent clockwise and counter-clockwise periodic motion. As a result, we argued in (1) that ((1)) represents a dynamic probability. The $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ functions may take on positive and negative values and so there can be interference, something seen in classical physics for physical waves (sound, water etc), but here representing probability.

Dynamical Probability Versus Static Probability

We argued above that $\exp(ipx)$ represents dynamic probability because its value changes for p and $-p$. It is useful for dynamic problems such as motion through two slits as one has two different rays describing motion through one slit and the other and the corresponding $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ functions interfere. We argue, however, that not all problems focus on dynamics. For example, if one considers kinetic energy, then:

$$\begin{aligned} p^2/2m &= -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \cos(px) / \cos(px) \\ &= -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \sin(px) / \sin(px) \quad ((2)) \end{aligned}$$

In other words, the dynamical form $\exp(ipx)$, which was required for two slit interference, is not required to calculate kinetic energy as either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ suffice. As a result, we argue that for a situation in which one only considers energy, one does not need to worry about the dynamical features, i.e. the complex portion. This has implications for a single particle bound state problem analyzed in terms of energy. Classical mechanics already shows that one may consider such a problem in terms of conservation of energy using kinetic energy plus potential energy $V(x)$ equalling a constant energy. Thus, we argue that one may write (for different parities)

$$-1/2m (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \cos(px)) / (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \cos(px)) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3A)) \text{ or}$$

$$-1/2m (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \sin(px)) / (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \sin(px)) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3B))$$

((3)) does not consider the dynamic features of $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. $(\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \cos(px))$ and $(\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \sin(px))$ are real functions. Does this mean that a bound single particle does not move in one direction for some time and then in the other? We argue that it must if high energy quantum mechanics is to be consistent with classical mechanics as dictated by the correspondence principle. The point is that a complex wavefunction is not needed at any energy level to find $a(p)$ values if one considers energy conservation. Thus, energy conservation has the sense of an equilibrium calculation, even though physically there is motion to the right and then to the left, especially at high energy levels. This seems to imply that the one average motion to the right and left which is exactly what $\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)$ or $\exp(ipx)-\exp(-ipx)$ yields. As a result, including both p and $-p$ is a statistical averaging process applied to a situation in which there is distinct motion to the right or left. This distinct motion is irrelevant for an energy conservation equation because both p and $-p$ have the same kinetic energy. In other words, dynamically they are distinguishable because they represent motion in one direction or another, but in terms of energy analysis they are not. We argue that this is the interpretation that should be made. As a result, we have suggested that if one compares the Schrodinger equation for high energy values to classical motion, one needs to remember that there is actually a complex portion to the wavefunction because there is actually motion to the right for some time, followed by motion to the left.

Spatial Probability

It seems that there are two spatial probabilistic schemes in quantum mechanics and these appear

already at the free particle level. The free wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ depends on x and differs for p and $-p$ and describes motion associated with momentum in space. It is used for interactions, like two slit interactions. Only one component of $\exp(ipx)$ is needed for average kinetic energy calculations, however. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with dynamical paths in space or energy considerations, but there is a third consideration, the probability weight assigned to each point x . For constant p , i.e. constant motion, each x point should carry the same weight, but $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ by themselves have different weights. It is only the magnitude which suggests overall weights in space and these are independent of p or kinetic energy.

What happens in the case of single particle bound state? We argued that if one uses energy conservation considerations, one need only consider one component of $\exp(ipx)$ and create a linear superposition using various p values. Conservation of energy yields the weights of $a(p)$. How is the spatial probability then calculated? Traditionally, it is given by $W(x)W(x)$, but $W(x)$ is real, even though the particle should be moving to the right part of the time and then to the left. This is particularly true at high energy values. At low energy values, however, $\cos(px)$ pieces or $\sin(px)$ pieces range over \hbar/p lengths which may be significant with respect to the interval between classical turning points. Thus, one really cannot follow the particle in space and time and one does not really know if it is moving to the right or left. Thus, the average picture using p and $-p$ is fine at low energy levels and $W(x)W(x)$ does give the spatial probability. One, however, must be careful for high energies, because then one should be able to follow the particle as an $\exp(ipave(x)x)$ or $\exp(-ipave(x)x)$ depending on time as in the classical case. In such a situation, if dx is considered to be the highest resolvable length, the particle may be considered to have smooth motion, i.e. constant p within that region and a different p in the next dx .

The Question of Entropy

In the above section, we argued for the existence of two different probabilities even for a quantum free particle. The first is based strictly on $\exp(ipx)$, or more particularly with $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, because one or the other is all that is needed to describe kinetic energy. As a result, we argue that there is an energy associated with kinetic energy for a free particle which may be computed using Shannon's entropy, $S \text{ density} = -\cos(px) \ln(\cos(px))$ (or with $\sin(px)$) for a half cycle in which $\cos(px)$, or $\sin(px)$, is positive.

In the bound state case, one again has crests or troughs in the wavefunction and one may calculate an energy related entropy associated the absolute value of this wavefunction.

Spatial probability, however, seems to be a completely different matter, even though it is linked to $W(x)$. In the case of two slit interference, one is interested in the dynamics, i.e. the specific paths a particle takes if it passes through one slit or another. In such a case, one takes the modulus squared of: $\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(-ip \cdot r_2)$. For a single free particle, one takes the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ as probability density and then uses Shannon's entropy. For a bound state particle, one uses $W(x)W(x)$ as the probability.

As a result, we argue that one should consider two kinds of entropies as we have suggested in previous notes. We suggest that there exists an entropy already at the wavefunction level (i.e. one component of a complex wavefunction), which cannot be ignored as spatial weight are not the whole picture, a particle has energy as well and entropy associated with this. A free quantum particle is an example. All p , hence all $pp/2m$, values have the same equally weighted x points in terms of overall dynamic motion, but not in terms of energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that quantum mechanics describes a free particle (with constant p) in terms of dynamic x and p dependent probability. Momentum is used because it responds to

force. This dynamic probability is two dimensional to show periodicity and is linked to, but not the same as, a probability describing weights in space. A free particle, regardless of its p , and hence kinetic energy, has equally weighted x points. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ represents dynamical probability, while its modulus, weight in space. We argue further, that only one component of $\exp(ipx)$, either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, is needed to describe energy considerations. Thus, for a single particle bound state problem, analyzed in terms of energy conservation, one need only use $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, depending on the parity. This has the semblance of an equilibrium situation, because $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ may be constructed using $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$. For low energy situations for which \hbar/p is significant with respect to the interval between classical turning points, one really does not know if the particle is moving to the right or left. We argue that as energy increases, the system becomes more classical and there is distinct motion to the left or right, but a real wavefunction still applies in the sense that one only needs $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ to calculate weights when using energy conservation because such conservation does not distinguish between p and $-p$. As a result, we argue that the Schrodinger equation uses p and $-p$ averages, but this does not mean that there cannot be distinct motion to the right or left, especially for high energy levels. One may even use p and $-p$ average classically if using energy, but again that does not mean that there is not motion to the left for some time, followed by motion to the right.

We suggest that given that $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ is needed in energy analysis, there is an entropy associated with probability, or its superposition in the bound state case. One may use the absolute value of the real wavefunction for a bound state or the absolute value of $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ for a free particle to calculate this entropy.

There exists, however, a second entropy associated with spatial weights which follows from the modulus of the wavefunction. This seems to be a different kind of entropy.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Dynamical Probability Wave (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Alternative Quantum Entropy Including Stochastic Potential Hits (preprint, zenodo, 2020)